

GEOGRAPHICAL SCIENCES

A NOVEL APPROACH TO ESTIMATING THE SHARE OF UNDERGROUND FEEDING OF RIVERS

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ABSTRACT

The surface runoff of rivers can usually be measured by various methods at hydrometeorological stations. However, calculating the fraction of underground feeding (baseflow) of rivers is a very difficult hydrologic sphere. For this purpose, step-by-step and indirect methods are often used in hydrology. In the article, a new hydrological approach is proposed to determine the infiltration properties of soils and the underground share in the nutrition of rivers. The new method allows us to estimate the fraction of underground water in the river basin with any geographical conditions, with or without observation data. The baseflow in the rivers of the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus located in the Republic of Azerbaijan was calculated using the new approach, and it was found that there was a very small difference between the actual and the results obtained with our proposed methodology. Thus, in 73 cases this difference did not exceed $\pm 10\%$, and in only 27 cases the error was slightly higher than 10%.

Keywords: new scientific approach, surface runoff, underground feeding of rivers, infiltration, flow formation process.

INTRODUCTION

The study of the role of groundwater in terms of feeding rivers and determining its share in the water balance is considered one of the difficult and understudied areas of hydrology. Due to the difficulties of studying groundwater as a source of nutrition for rivers, in most cases its share has been determined by quantitative indicators of the remaining part after calculating other water balance elements. Despite this, it is possible to see that a lot of scientific research work has been carried out in this area in certain periods. [5, 7, 11, 14].

In the article we present, a new approach is proposed to calculate the water balance elements of rivers, including infiltration and the amount of groundwater in river feeding. The methodology was developed based on the synthesis of existing methodologies in this field in the world, selecting their superior features for our republic and making our own additions.

Previously, assessments of the elements of land moisture and water balance were carried out mainly with precipitation and temperature quantities, but now the direction of scientific approaches has changed significantly. Because modern science requires the solution of water-related issues not only in a multi-year period, but also within a more specific time and space. While meteorological indicators for that period can play the role of basic data for the assessment in the medium-long term, they lose their importance within a specific time-space framework, and in such situations, the moisture content of the area and the moisture level

of the soil become the main factors. That is, when assessing the water balance of the area at any given moment, the precipitation and temperature quantities lose their role as the main factor in that specific situation. Thus, despite the warm period, the degree of moisture in the area may be high, or vice versa. Thus, although precipitation and temperature are the main factors affecting the degree of moisture in the area, they are not considered valid quantities for the operational solution of water-related issues in a more specific area selection and time period. The research work carried out with the new approach proposed by us, in addition to eliminating the existing time-space dependence mentioned above, allows for faster and more accurate implementation of the problems. Since the research is carried out on the basis of a multispectral spatial image of the area, the dependence on the spatial factor is eliminated.

The formation of river flow is a very complex process [2, 4, 6, 9]. It is known that the water balance of river basins is associated with the division of precipitation falling into the basin into 3 parts: surface runoff, infiltration and actual evaporation. In the average multi-year period, the total runoff of rivers consists of surface and underground feeding shares.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The southern slope of the Greater Caucasus Mountains, located within the Republic of Azerbaijan, was chosen as the research area (Figure 1). The rivers here are the most abundant in Azerbaijan.

Figure 1. Location of the study area in the Republic of Azerbaijan

Satellite images of different years, a digital elevation model (DEM-Digital Elevation Model) and hydro-meteorological observation data were used as the source materials for the research. Data on the landscape-soil fund were obtained on the basis of fragments of multispectral (hyperspectral) satellite images. Height, slope, and exposure measurements were determined using DTM, and river morphometric values were determined using ArcGIS Hydrology, Surface, Density, and other software.

In terms of river runoff assessment, the Rational method and the NRCS-CN method are considered the most important hydrological methods in the world.

The Rational method is considered one of the most important method for assessing the level of precipitation formation on surface runoff. The formula of the rational method (Rational Equation) is expressed as follows:

$$Q = ciA \quad (1)$$

Here Q – is the water discharge (unit-cubic feet), i – is the amount of precipitation (inch), A – is the area of the study area (acre), c – is the rational (surface) runoff coefficient. The rational coefficient is found on the basis of various types of landscape, hydrological soil groups (HSGs) and slope.

Runoff Curve Numbers (CN) used in the NRCS-CN method are also indicators definition of the precipitation rate to runoff formation. In this method, the conversion rates of precipitation to runoff are expressed by different runoff curve numbers (CN) at 3 humidity levels (dry, normal, saturated). Unlike the Rational method, an important advantage of the NRCS-CN method is that, with the possibilities of determining surface runoff, it simultaneously reflects the infiltration

characteristics of the area, especially in terms of assessing the degree of soil moisture. This feature is especially important in content of estimating the share of underground feeding of rivers (baseflow). In NRCS-CN method uses several important components to determine the water balance of an area as:

- 1) Hydrological losses (L) – is the fraction of precipitation that does not participate in the formation of surface runoff.
- 2) Maximum soil retention (S) – is maximum water retention capacity of soils in the concrete physical and geographical conditions of the territory.
- 3) Initial abstraction (I_a) – is part of precipitation spent on various areas before surface runoff formation.
- 4) Actual soil moisture (F) – is the actual soil water retention under the existing geographical conditions of the area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The role of groundwater in the water balance of the territory and in the nutrition of rivers has been studied in the following 4 directions [1, 3, 8, 13]:

- 1) As an integral element of a single river system along with the surface flow of groundwater.
- 2) As a participant in the humidity balance of the territory and a soil moisturizer.
- 3) As an influencer of groundwater in the river's nutritional regime and a regulator of the rivers runoff.
- 4) As an important participant in the nutrition of the river and an underground organizer.

The main content of considering groundwater as an integral element of a single system along with surface flow in a river basin is that groundwater plays a basic role in the formation of the river basin and, due to their activity, the functioning of the water system as a whole is ensured continuously. Therefore, when

assessing and predicting the elements of the water balance of any territory, water resources, water loss and other risks, the degree of soil moisture, water absorption capacity, and the level of their nutrition of groundwater must be taken into account.

The contribution of the underground organizer to the river's nutrition and its role in the formation of the river flow were assessed in three ways:

1) By comparing basins with similar morphometric indicators but sharply different geological structures and water flows.

2) By dividing the hydrographs of rivers according to their nutrient sources.

3) By applying the remaining part to underground nutrition after calculating the surface runoff and evaporation quantities in the water balance.

With a new scientific approach, it is possible to eliminate the existing shortcomings and subjective aspects in this area, and the groundwater flow is calculated in the following sequence:

1) Based on modern leading methodologies, a rational runoff coefficient (c), which specifically indicates the part of the precipitation (P) that is

converted into surface runoff at the time of precipitation, and hydrological losses (L), maximum soil water retention (S), initial abstraction (I_a) and actual soil moisture (F) corresponding to those conditions are found.

2) In order to calculate the water balance elements in the dry and perennial periods, including the share of groundwater fraction, the moisture conditions of the river basins were taken into account. Thus, correction factors were determined for the transition from short-term wet (precipitation) conditions to the perennial period, taking into account drought conditions.

3) The groundwater runoff in the rivers was determined using the formula we proposed [10, 12].

$$U = (L \times \frac{F}{S}) \quad (2)$$

The role of groundwater in the nutrition of rivers was investigated using the example of the rivers of the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus. Table 1 shows a comparison of the actual and obtained by new approach values of the groundwater feeding share of the rivers.

Table 1

Comparison of the actual and new calculated values of the groundwater nutrition share of the rivers of the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus

Rivers	Underground feeding of the rivers		
	Factual, mm	Calculated with new method, mm	Difference, %
Mazym	183.2	202.6	+9.57
Balaken	198.2	226.9	+12.6
Katekh	261.3	245.2	-6.16
Tala	238.2	220.7	-7.35
Mukhakh	210.4	231.0	+8.92
Kapychay	165.7	176.9	+6.33
Kurmukh	254.1	250.4	-1.46
Kashkachay	143.1	168.6	+15.1
Dashagıl	262.4	235.5	-10.3
Eyrichay	181.3	169.8	-6.34
Alijan	98.6	105.4	+6.45
Turyanchay	187.7	169.4	-9.74
Goychay	90.8	95.7	+5.12
Girdiman	129.4	146.3	+11.6
Aksu	60.7	56.0	-7.74
Pirsaat	36.2	38.8	+6.70
Jeyrankechmez	0.81	1.07	+24.3
Sumqayıt	19.6	5.29	+3.45

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